

Contact Center Knowledge Management Tool using Decision Tree

Dhanya D T
*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
(Cyber Security)
Presidency University
Bengaluru , India*
dhanya.20221CCS00115@pre
sidencyuniversity.in

C Niharika
*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
(Cyber Security)
Presidency University
Bengaluru , India*
niharika.20221CCS0113@pre
sidencyuniversity.in

Bhavani
*Department of Computer
Science and Engineering
(Cyber Security)
Presidency University
Bengaluru , India*
bhavani.20221CCS0128@pre
sidencyuniversity.in

Dr. Anandaraj S. P
*Head of Department , School
of Computer Science and
Engineering (CCS, CIT, CSG)
Presidency University
Bengaluru , India*
hod.cse8@presidencyuniver
sity.in

*Ms.Raesa Razeen
Assistant Professor, School of
Computer Science and
Engineering
Presidency University
Bengaluru , India*
sharmasth.vali@presidencyun
iversity.in

Abstract :- In the current scenarios digital customer service keeps changing rapidly, managing smartly has become key to improving customer experience and efficiency. In this paper, we propose a system called SupportIQ a knowledge based Decision tree framework(KBDTF) designed to make customer support faster, accurate, reliable and consistent. The proposed system brings together decision-tree logic and semantic knowledge retrieval layer that relies on machine learning and natural language processing (NLP). The framework will offer context-aware decisions and handle queries quickly. The question and answer flow will be complemented by hybrid semantic search that uses Sentence Transformer model. SupportIQ has been implemented using modular flask architecture so it can easily scale across varied service categories such as billing, account management, network troubleshooting. During testing, experimental results showed large reduction in response time and improvement in user satisfaction metrics. SupportIQ places itself as a pragmatic and transparent AI-powered solution for automating contact center operations due to its interpretability, adaptability and modular composition.

Keywords :- Knowledge Management; Decision Tree; Contact Centre; Customer Satisfaction; Knowledge-Based Decision Support System; Machine Learning; Artificial Intelligence; Modular Architecture; Knowledge Retrieval; Service Optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of any organization in the current digital world depends on customer experience and their feedback. Complex services and businesses use contact centers as primary interaction points. However, given the advancement in technology traditional customer support systems will face problems like repeated queries, huge repositories. In addition to that, delayed responses, inconsistent delivery of information will lead to decline in user satisfaction.

The use of AI with Knowledge management has changed how customer service works. It now uses smart and automated systems to help customers. Knowledge Based Decision Support System (KBDSS) is an example of intelligent system which has been used in industries for a long period of time. It shows how combination of rule-

based reasoning with data-driven learning leads to improvement in decision-making under any uncertainty.

Our paper discusses about SupportIQ, a Knowledge-Based Decision Tree Framework, that aims to help both the customers and support agents to solve queries quickly with the help of structured FAQs and dynamically updated knowledge bases. Unlike many AI models that work similar to black-box, SupportIQ uses decision trees that are clear and explainable. It makes every decision path traceable and understandable to both users and administrators.

SupportIQ uses a hybrid model that is implemented using a lightweight web framework Flask. It helps with routing. Rendering and integration with various extensions. Jinja2 is used as template engine to create dynamic HTML pages. The backend logic handles user request and interacts with SQLite database using SQLAlchemy for ORM data. Client interactions are enhanced with HTMCSS, JavaScript with extended integration of EmailJS and Google reCAPTCHA for security.

Building on prior research into KBDSS, modular software engineering, and decision tree-based analytics, this study extends multidisciplinary findings to the domain of contact center. The combination of knowledge bases, decision trees and modular architecture helps to perceive a better, consistent and intelligent real time support. SupportIQ basically demonstrates how the integration of semantic knowledge management, interpretable machine learning, and modular system design can provide better response times, consistent service quality, and tangible improvements in customer satisfaction on the way to the next generation of intelligent, transparent, and scalable contact center solutions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge-Based Decision Support Systems (KBDSS) have been recognized from a long time for combining domain knowledge with algorithmic reasoning (Sivakumar et al, Turban et al) [2]. Contemporary contact centers have the capacity to integrate KBDSS with decision tree models that helps to organize customer

queries logically and provide responses based on the historical interactions (Rokach and Maimon) [3]. Semantic knowledge management provides context aware data representation that provides better efficiency regarding contact center systems (Liao, IGI Global) [5]. The modular architecture helps to separate the data, process knowledge and present independent layers (Cai et al) [7]. In addition to that, decision tree models like C4.5 and CART have been used to analyze customer satisfaction by considering key factors such as response time, communication clarity (Quinlan, Tsami et al) [9].

2.5 Research Gap and Contribution

While these studies provide valuable insights, there is need to address important gaps like combining semantic knowledge management with modular design to provide real time working contact center systems that can grow as needed. Currently platforms do not provide platforms with easy to understand decision processes which in turn makes it hard for the users to trust system outputs. It's also complex to handle huge range of customer questions that evolve over time. This can lead to slow and inconsistent results. Individual models exist but they do not integrate various aspects of contact centers.

Therefore, SupportIQ is an attempt to fill these gaps to provide a model that combines semantic knowledge management, decision tree models and modular architecture. It aims to provide fast and consistent decision-making model that can quickly adapt to dynamic customer needs.

3. METHODOLOGY

SupportIQ helps to make easy real-time decisions by following a modular and structured approach to deal with data. The model first collects the knowledge, uses semantic embeddings to create summaries. It then follows decision tree approach to help user make choices. Finally, it integrates the whole system together, making the system and support experience smooth and effective. This employs the best bits of KBDSS, machine learning classification, and modular software architecture, all adding up to a system that can turn raw interaction data into a useful and intelligent knowledge system. And this gives you the power to boost customer satisfaction, cut

down on query resolution time and make knowledge retrieval in a contact centre much more efficient.

Fig.3.1:User Interaction Flow

3.1 Knowledge Acquisition and Knowledge Base Construction

The SupportIQ framework puts all its focus on building up a complete Knowledge Base as the go-to list for all the knowledge in a particular area. Information has been collected and put together using a combination of external sources and organization-specific details to get a full picture.

Here, Python helps to process the data and load its scripts from CSV files to dataframes. Further, it preprocesses them. The model generates semantic embeddings using a pre trained model all-miniLM, that uses a library called sentence-transformers. These embeddings have traditional TF-IDF vectorization. It implements hybrid retrieval model that helps to build decision trees that support real time decisions.

There are three main domains/categories that the model supports. The categories are:

- Network Troubleshooting
- Billing and Payment Issues
- Account Management and Security

These categories were implemented in the database through the file seed_data.py, which defines hierarchical question–answer flows forming the logical structure of the decision tree.

3.2 Semantic Processing and Embedding Generation

SupportIQ uses semantic embeddings to understand user queries even if the order or phrasing differs. It uses sentence transformer library that will convert data into numerical vectors called embeddings. Embeddings give relation between texts that helps to recognize that queries like “Why is my Wifi not connecting?” and “My internet is not working” which have similar meaning but different words. This helps in accurate information and to understand, respond to customer queries easily.

We store all these vectors in embeddings file, to make it easy to scan them fast when someone asks a question - and this semantic base helps Support IQ do more than just search around for keywords to give you an answer. Instead, it gives content that is accurate.

3.3 Hybrid Semantic Retrieval Mechanism

1. TF-IDF Vectorization: Lexical similarity is determined using term frequency and inverse document frequency.

2. Semantic Embeddings: Applying cosine similarity for the semantic matching between user requests and stored information.

The system first looks for a perfect match in the pre-defined FAQs, when there is a query. If no such document exists, the retriever calculates cosine similarity between the query embedding and the stored-degree knowledge embeddings. Best match response is chosen only if the similarity is above this threshold (0.3 by default).

Therefore, it uses a two-layer retrieval approach considering precision and generalization.

TF-IDF guarantees that matches are appropriate for certain terms. Semantic representations encode the meaning and contextual relevance of natural language questions. Should the threshold not be met, the system gracefully degrades itself by providing a fallback message, or escalating it to manual support.

3.4 Decision Tree–Based Query Handling

SupportIQ also uses a Decision Tree Framework for guided query resolution. The app, built along database models defined in various python scripts. It involves:

- tree structure: has a follow-up question (tree branching), or
- This is the solution_text, and there are no more ways to continue from here.

For example, in the “Network Troubleshooting” flow:

1. The user is first asked whether the router is powered on.
2. If “No,” then the process instructs them to power up the router.
3. "YES", and if so, the system advances to whether modem lights are steady.
4. If the instability persists, then the system will pull up from its knowledge base, the article "Restarting Your Router Properly" with step-by-step guidance.

This is the dynamical flow that shall make this reasoning consistent and therefore provide an efficient and adaptable customer support via interpretable decision paths.

3.5 System Implementation and Integration

The final tool is deployed as a Flask web app (app.py) that consolidates the back-end functionality, database schema, and front-of-site content.

• Backend Services:

Flask deals with routing, RESTful API endpoints and communication between the retriever, decision tree and front-end interface. The decision-tree is where SQLAlchemy ORM keeps persisted data.

• APIs and Endpoints:

Dynamic: /chat, /category/<id>/json, and such routes. These calls allow for users to directly interact with the backend as there are dynamic flows involved there like real-time queries and chatbot responses.

• User Interface:

Constructed using HTML templates (base.html, chatbot.html, categories.html, and contact.html) the UI has a floating chatbot widget, smooth scrolling effect, and a form to submit feedbacks directly through EmailJS.

• Integration of Hybrid Retrieval:

Context-based answers are enabled and logical traceability is maintained by the integrated retriever of decision-tree-flows.

Fig.3.5.1: Decision Tree + Hybrid Retrieval Workflow

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

SupportIQ architecture is organized in a tiered architecture. Each layer handles a specific function like data handling, semantic processing, decision making and user interaction. The layered architecture helps to update easily, ensuring that new features involving NLP models can be added easily without making any changes in existing components.

4.1 Overview of Architectural Design

The architecture has three main operating categories like:

1. Data Management and Knowledge Representation
2. Intelligent Decision-Making and Semantic Retrieval
3. User Interaction and Service Delivery

These categories interact with each through APIs that help to connect backend and frontend seamlessly

Fig.4.1: Layers of Architecture

4.2 Data Layer

The model's base foundation is Data Layer. It handles aspects like data storage and retrieval, including both structured and unstructured data.

The layer contains the following components:

- **SQLite Database:** This uses SQLAlchemy ORM which stores data like categories, questions, answers and user sessions. The logical connections between the decision tree and user interactions are shown in these tables. Domains like Network, Billing, and Account Management are defined by category. Hierarchical decision paths are defined by question and answer tables. Knowledge articles offers comprehensive technical solutions associated with particular decision nodes. User progress and outstanding issues are tracked by the session and escalation tables.

- **Knowledge Base Files:** The unstructured knowledge repository contains text snippets extracted from Wikipedia and internal documents. Each textual segment functions as an important knowledge unit.
- **Embeddings and Metadata:** Embeddings provide the fast computation of cosine similarity for retrieval tasks by storing semantic representations. This layer ensures that the data is consistent, accessible, and intact so that higher layers can make decisions and retrieve data efficiently.

4.3 Knowledge processing layer

Raw text data is converted into organized, machine-readable knowledge representations by the Knowledge Processing Layer. It carries out the following essential tasks:

- **Data cleaning and chunking:** For best retrieval, large textual content is divided into manageable chunks using the `build_kb.py` script.
- **Semantic embedding generations:** The Sentence Transformer (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) model is used to encode each text segment into high-dimensional vectors using `generate_embeddings.py`. The system can recognize conceptual connections between user queries and stored content thanks to these embeddings, which capture each text's semantic meaning.
- **Knowledge Indexing:** To allow for quick search of similar items, we index the embeddings with their texts. Indexed knowledge links the knowledge repository and the decision support layer together.

This layer ensures that the query interpretation is human-like and contextually accurate by making the system understand the user's intent and not merely keywords.

4.4 Decision support layer

- **Hybrid semantic retrieval:** The `retriever.py` module of the transformers includes a retriever. The retriever finds the correct answers by using cosine similarity on the semantic embeddings and TF-IDF vectors. If the decision tree or the FAQs do not contain a match

the retriever can still retrieve the next best answer based on similarity.

- **Reasoning and escalation handling:** Additionally, it logs any instances that the chatbot cannot resolve independently for future analysis. This information is stored in the Session and Escalation tables. It is part of the continual learning process to enhance the models and knowledge base for future iterations.

The system will need to have an easy input which is clear and understandable for the user.

4.5 Application layer

SupportIQ's user interface (UI) and overall interaction experience are represented by the Presentation Layer. This layer has HTML, Bootstrap and JavaScript. The chatbot interface handles real-time user queries via JavaScript that fetches the API and combines semantic and decision-tree based responses. Decision tree visualizations provide navigation of decision paths through dynamic question-answers cards. FAQ and contact modules improve system interactions and user engagement.

5. CONCLUSION

As customer interactions continue to grow more and more complex in today's digital world, it is necessary for the contact center systems to advance and be dynamic. The given framework successfully blends KBDSS, ML models and modular architecture that helps to know the extent of customer satisfaction, referring to Tsami et al. It is designed to smoothly integrate with CRM and support tools. In Discovering Trends and Journeys in Knowledge-based management, the sections on knowledge sharing and trend analysis further emphasizes that from a data-driven perspective, there will be an improvement in the customer experience as well as the agent performance and decision quality.

By integrating these foundations from diverse fields, the application and fit of the proposed model are enhanced. Following are some of the potential benefits associated with the framework framework: a decrease in knowledge retrieval time, a decrease in query resolution efforts, an increase in consistent decision-making and measurable

customer satisfaction improvement. It helps to provide a broad vision of organizations enhancing the quality of their deliveries through constant feedback.

The future work can extend the system with natural language processing to facilitate automatic interpretation of the query, analyze the sentiment in real-time and adapt hybrid models combining decision trees with deep learning for sophisticated query handling.

To summarise, the Knowledge-Based Decision Tree framework shows how integrated structure of knowledge management with ML provides better customer satisfaction and insights. A dynamic knowledge base that can continuously learn and update will help to improve performance over time. Overall, this framework helps to deliver faster, accurate and operational efficiency.

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